

How to Create Sustainable Future through Curriculum in Higher Education

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Abstract

Sustainable Development has been the core concept of society development for the last decades. The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development has become the turning point in new global Sustainable Development framework. Education as a key instrument plays one of the important roles in promoting Sustainable Development philosophy including 17 Sustainable Development Goals among society to empower everyone to contribute to achieving the ambitious and crucial global Agenda. Integration of Sustainable Development Goals in educational and research programs allows to involve education representatives, policy makers, civil society actors and other stakeholders in raising awareness, generating knowledge and making decisions focused on three Sustainable Development dimensions – economic, social and environmental ones at different levels. The objective of this paper is to define inclusion of Sustainable Development aspects in curriculum in Higher Education Institutions and identify teaching tools and methods to motivate students to get new knowledge in Sustainable Development Goals, transform their behaviour for sustainable future and disseminate Sustainable Development values among wide range of stakeholders – business society, local and regional authorities and communities, etc. This paper presents a review of five year-experience in integrating Sustainable Development values and principles in curriculum accumulated by National Research Mordovia State University. The study is based on content analysis of Master's programs curriculum, qualitative analysis of perceived values and challenges relating to Sustainable Development Goals in the view of Master students and their inputs to the goals achievements. The findings illustrate some measures that may be adopted in order to enhance methodology and develop teaching tools to integrate Sustainable Development philosophy in Higher Education Institutions' curriculum. It also should be reinforced at different levels of University programs in different subject fields.

Keywords: sustainable development goals; higher education for sustainable development; curriculum; interdisciplinarity; values; behaviour.

1 Introduction

Sustainable development (SD) is considered as a holistic and integrative concept that combines different dimensions and values from the perspective of economic, social and environmental aspects and their impact on future generations. Discussions about the term 'sustainability' in the academic circles and society continue despite its definition mentioned in the Brundtland Report as "development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs" (World Commission on Environment and Development, 1987). A common ground for different definitions of SD does exist and is summarised by Leal Filho *et al* (2009):

(a) refers to long-term prospects with ecological, political, economic and societal implications, (b) is a dynamic process, whose implementation depends on due consideration of social processes of which individual engagement and participation are essential elements and (c) depends on concerted efforts and cannot be based on action by a few countries or local actors if it is to be implemented on a global level.

The 2030 Agenda for SD (United Nations, 2015) has become the turning point in new global SD framework. The 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are global in nature, universally applicable and interlinked.

Education plays one of the important roles in promoting the SD philosophy including SDGs among society to empower everyone to contribute to achieving the ambitious and crucial global Agenda. Engaging society in sustainable-related issues and making individuals sustainability change-makers require the knowledge, skills, values and attitudes that will empower them to take informed decisions and responsible actions for environmental integrity, economic viability and just society for present and future generations.

Education is considered both as “a goal in itself and a means for achieving all the other SDGs. It is not only an integral part of sustainable development, but also a key enabler for it” (UNESCO, 2017). Many HEIs worldwide are implementing strategies for attaining 17 SDGs through a whole institutional approach. The approach involves rethinking the curriculum, campus operations, organizational culture, student participation, leadership and management, community, relationships and research. Applying the whole institutional approach to implement the new philosophy at University may require even reframing HEI’s vision, mission and values and restructuring it according to the priorities. Reorganization and reframing will necessitate extensive resources in certain cases but outputs be worth it (Maykova et al, 2017).

First of all, mainstreaming SD in education requires integrating SD issues into curriculum. Development of sustainable curriculum allows to improve the capacity of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) to prepare people to pursue SD through changing their values and motivation, upgrading their knowledge, transforming their behaviour (Salimova et al, 2015). Young people will play a crucial role in achieving the SDGs since they have more to offer the challenge of SD; they have the skills and energy to deliver impact now. In 2025 the global student population in Further and Higher Education will reach more than 260 million (Goddard, 2011). Therefore students are becoming active agents in achieving SDGs that requires development of specific competences relevant to all goals.

Competences cannot be taught but have to be developed by the learners themselves. They are acquired during action on the basis of experience and reflection (UNESCO, 2015a). According to the UNESCO Competences Framework (UNESCO, 2017) the cross-cutting competences are crucial to be developed: systems thinking, anticipatory, normative and strategic competencies, collaboration, critical thinking, self-awareness and integrated problem-solving.

The competences are essential for applying available knowledge and expertise to address particular sustainability issues at a systemic level (in the social sphere and in policy-making), but they also work at a personal level guiding individual choices and lifestyle formation (Stoof *et al*, 2002; Dlouhá *et al*, 2019; Wamsler, 2020). It is for this reason that one of the key principles of the study is moving from a teacher-centred to a student-oriented approach. So, in other words, the teacher and the student collaborate in learning through the following “domains”: “Learning to know”→“Learning to do”→“Learning to live together”→“Learning to be”. Therefore, the importance of active learning strategies as a device to enhance meaningful learning and provide evidence from students that it helps to increase their engagement in learning are increasing (Fernandes *et al*, 2014).

This paper provides a reflexive case study of Master students’ consciousness about SD priorities and their opportunities to achieve the SDGs. Therefore, the purpose of the study is to define inclusion of SD aspects in HEI curriculum and identify teaching tools and methods to transform students behavior for sustainable future and disseminate SD values among wide range of stakeholders – business society, local and regional authorities and communities, etc.

2 Materials and Methods

The study draws on different types of methods, such as content analysis of Master’s programs curriculum, qualitative analysis of perceived values and challenges relating to SDGs from views of Master students in 2016-2020 academic years and mind mapping of the students inputs on the SDGs achievement. It should be noted that the study of student reflections is a part of the course “Sustainable Development Management”.

2.1 Data collection

Data collection during the study included 2 stages. In the opening stage of the study Master’s programs curricula implemented at National Research Mordovia State University were collected. It was revealed that 10 out of 83 Master’s programs curricula implemented in 2016-2020 academic years included different SD aspects. The second stage included the study of Master students’ viewpoints as to SDGs’ achievement. Participants for this study comprised 156 students enrolled for the course “Sustainable Development Management”, represented two different Master’s programs: “Entrepreneurship for Sustainable Development” and “Integrated Management Systems” in 2016-2020 academic years. The reflective thinking tasks were developed with regard

to a SDGs perspective, aiming to explore students' perceived values and challenges related to SDGs. For ethical reasons, some of the background information on the students – such as age and the country of origin – was not accounted in the study. It was suggested to use the following framework to complete the task:

- Specify the SDGs that you consider to be priority and most important for development of mankind future.
- Make a critical reflection about your contribution to achieve each of 17 SDGs.

The students uploaded their responses to the reflective thinking tasks to the University eLearning environment system. These responses were extracted from the system and compiled in an excel file. The excel file was used for the value analysis and mind-mapping that showed reflection on inclusion of the students in achieving SDGs.

2.2 Data analysis

For the purposes of the study a set of methods were formed following the UNESCO Competences Framework and taking into account the necessity to develop cross-cutting competences of students both at the systemic and the individual levels. Therefore, content analysis of Master's programs curriculum refers to the systemic level and allows to identify the capacity of HEIs to upgrade students' knowledge in SD. Qualitative analysis of Master students' values provides with evaluation of students' behaviour transformation and their readiness to be involved in communities and joint activities. Analysis of results received from critical reflection about students' contribution to the SDGs achievement enables to identify their values and motivation to act as active agents in achieving SDGs and disseminate SD values among wide range of stakeholders – business society, local and regional authorities and communities.

At the first stage content analysis of Master's programs curricula were carried out. As a result of collecting Master programs implemented at the University 10 programs were selected. The criterion for selection of the programs was their Sustainable Development orientation.

Holsti (1968) defined content analysis as "any technique for making inferences by systematically and objectively identifying special characteristics of messages". Content analysis is a research tool used to determine the presence of certain issues, aspects, themes, or concepts within some given qualitative data (i.e. text). Using content analysis, it is possible to quantify and analyze the presence and, meanings of such certain points. In relation to our study the content analysis of Master programs curricula allowed to identify the programs focused on different SD dimensions. To meet the requirement, the methodology offered by Colombo & Alves (2017) studying sustainability in engineering programs, was applied. The curriculum of each Master program implemented at the University was analyzed and the courses with a title related to the SD dimensions – Environmental, Social and Economic were counted and registered in an excel file. After the courses were identified their objectives and learning outcomes were interpreted and analyzed.

The next stage of the study was supposed to include analysis of qualitative data received by the students' reflection on priority and most important SDGs for development of mankind future and their contribution to achieve each of them.

Bhattacharjee (2012) defined qualitative analysis as the analysis of qualitative data such as text data from interview transcript. The emphasis in qualitative analysis is "sense making" or understanding a phenomena. A creative and investigative mindset is needed for qualitative analysis, based on an ethically enlightened and participant-in-context attitude, and a set of analytic strategies.

At the final stage of carrying out the analysis mind mapping as a tool of structuration and visualisation of students inputs to the SDGs achievement was applied. The mind map allowed to represent a variety of students' views and main patterns of their potential contribution to attaining SDGs and evaluate importance of the goals from the perspective of students' perception.

3 Results and Discussion

Results of the content analysis of 10 Master's programs curricula carried out from the perspective of SD dimensions are showed in Table 1.

Table 1. Sustainable Development Dimensions of Master's programs.

Master programs	Sustainable Development Dimensions		
	Environmental	Social	Economic
Green Building	√	√	
Ecology and materials, products, structures saving in Construction	√		√
Geocology	√		
Environmental management	√		√
Ecology	√		
Fundamental biotechnology	√		
Cultural heritage preservation		√	
Social protection and social services for families and children		√	
Integrated Management System	√	√	√
Entrepreneurship for Sustainable Development	√	√	√

The analysis revealed that only 2 out of 10 Master's programs curricula contained all three SD dimensions – environmental, social and economic ones: Integrated Management System and Entrepreneurship for Sustainable Development. 3 Master's programs curricula include two aspects: Ecology and materials, products, structures saving in Construction and Environmental management were focused on environmental and economic dimensions, Green Building – environmental and social ones. 5 Master's programs curricula were targeted at separate SD issues – environmental or social one. Environmental dimension dominated in 8 out of 10 Master's programs curricula.

For further analysis purposes 156 students enrolled for two Master's programs in 2016-2020 academic years - Integrated Management System and Entrepreneurship for Sustainable Development which contained all three SD dimensions (30-40 students per year at average) were involved in the study.

Answering a question about the priority of SDGs for development of mankind future, students ranked each goal by significance from 0 – "lack of significance" to 1 – "the key priority". Thus, each goal could score a maximum value of 1. The total value of all SDGs could be 17 based on the number of the goals. The criterion (quantitative) of the goals priority by year was identified at more than 0.5. The main results of the students' reflections are summarized below in Table 2 (average evaluation for each year and SDG).

Table 2. SDGs in perception of Master students (value analysis).

Year	1 NO POVERTY	2 ZERO HUNGER	3 GOOD HEALTH AND WELL-BEING	4 QUALITY EDUCATION	5 GENDER EQUALITY	6 CLEAN WATER AND SANITATION	7 AFFORDABLE AND CLEAN ENERGY	8 DECENT WORK AND ECONOMIC GROWTH	9 INDUSTRY, INNOVATION AND INFRASTRUCTURE	10 REDUCED INEQUALITIES	11 SUSTAINABLE CITIES AND COMMUNITIES	12 RESPONSIBLE CONSUMPTION AND PRODUCTION	13 CLIMATE ACTION	14 LIFE BELOW WATER	15 LIFE ON LAND	16 PEACE, JUSTICE AND STRONG INSTITUTIONS	17 PARTNERSHIP FOR THE GOALS
2020	0,83	0,94	0,88	0,94	0,88	0,94	0,88	0,88	0,82	0,67	0,79	0,83	0,94	0,71	0,94	0,82	0,76
2019	0,87	0,81	0,91	0,96	0,91	0,90	0,91	0,87	0,78	0,71	0,63	0,87	0,83	0,67	0,96	0,96	0,83
2018	0,73	0,76	0,95	0,85	0,48	0,96	0,80	0,65	0,49	0,53	0,49	0,75	0,80	0,56	0,89	0,75	0,55
2017	0,79	0,49	0,93	0,58	0,29	0,82	0,89	0,56	0,27	0,34	0,24	0,69	0,82	0,27	0,79	0,49	0,43
2016	0,82	0,36	0,87	0,45	0,18	0,73	0,91	0,36	0,18	0,19	0,17	0,50	0,64	0,20	0,82	0,36	0,18

Firstly, in 2016 only five SDGs (SDG1 – No poverty; SDG3 – Good health and well-being; SDG6 – Clean water and sanitation; SDG7 – Affordable and clean energy; SDG13 – Climate action) were marked as priority. Secondly, in 2017 the number of priority goals increased to 9. To the above mentioned goals SDG4 – Quality education; SDG8 – Decent work and economic growth; SDG 12 – Responsible consumption and production; SDG15 – Life on land were added. Thirdly, in 2018 other 5 goals were included in the students' priorities: SDG2 – Zero hunger; SDG10 – Reduced inequalities; SDG14 – Life below water; SDG16 – Peace, justice and strong institutions and SDG17 – Partnerships. Finally, in 2019 – 2020 academic years all 17 SDGs were identified by students as having priority for SD.

From the students' perspective, the highest priority goals, which value increased during the study period and in 2020 amounted to more than 0.9, have been SDG2 – Zero hunger, SDG3 – Good health and well-being, SDG6 – Clean water and sanitation, SDG13 – Climate action and SDG 15 – Life on land. At the same time, the greatest increase (more than 3 times) in value for the students is observed in relation to the following goals: SDG5 – Gender equality (4,8 times); SDG9 – Industry, innovation, and infrastructure (4,5 times); SDG10 – Reduced inequalities (3,5 times); SDG11 – Sustainable cities and communities (4,6 times); SDG14 – Life below water (3,5 times); SDG17 – Partnerships (3,3 times).

Therefore, qualitative analysis of students' reflections allowed to identify the increase in value of all 17 SDGs confirmed by the growth of the total evaluation – doubling in 5 years, from 7,92 in 2016 to 14,45 in 2020 (maximum estimation of the all SDGs' total value could be 17 as mentioned above).

As it was mentioned earlier mind mapping was used to visualise results of the students' reflections and their replies on the SDGs that reflected their values and motivation to contribute valuable input on achieving the SDGs. The students answered the question: "Please make a critical reflection about your contribution to achieve each of 17 SDGs". Segments of the students' most common reflections linked to each of 17 SDGs are presented in Figure 1. Most of their responses match the results of the qualitative analysis described above. The SDGs marked by the students as priority revealed more reflections and replies on their input to achieving the goals both now and in the future. They are SDG1 – No poverty; SDG2 – Zero hunger; SDG3 – Good health and well-being; SDG4 – Quality education; SDG13 – Climate action; SDG 15 – Life on land.

Their replies also reflect the use of knowledge and expertise to address particular sustainability issues both at the systemic and the personal levels. For instance, for SDG 15 – Life on land "use USB drive instead of paper" or "no buying a real New Year Tree" are an individual choice and "support National Parks and Nature Reserves" or "saving biodiversity ecosystems" are the decisions at the systemic level respectively. "Educate children and grandchildren saving seas and oceans" (for SDG 14 – Life below Water) highlights the students' views to attach much importance to SD issues not only now but in the future.

4 Conclusion

This paper presents the experience of National Research Mordovia State University in the roll-out of its approach to promoting the Sustainable Development oriented course as a means of embedding SDGs, research-based teaching and learning in the Master' programs curricula. The study shows the need for changes at both the systemic and the individual levels in the context of SD knowledge.

Regarding the systemic level the study shows the importance of expanding the number of programs that include all three SD dimensions – environmental, social and economic ones, as well as introduction of these programs with regard to their interdisciplinary approach. It also should be reinforced at different levels of the University programs in different subject fields.

For the individual level, the findings illustrate an approach that may be adopted to enhance the methodology and develop teaching tools to integrate the SD philosophy in HEI curriculum. Special attention should be paid to applying active learning strategies (Research based learning, Project and Problem based learning) to increase the level of students' awareness and consciousness regarding the importance of SDGs for current and future generations, and their inputs in achieving the goals. Emphasizing learning domains with regard to SD competences thus shows not only the needs for balanced development of the systemic and the individual levels, it also may help to identify desirable learning processes that may be initiated through appropriate active learning strategies.

To conclude, our findings suggests that linking students' values and perceptions regarding SDGs with their promoted actions will require to motivate them for getting new knowledge in SDGs, transform their behavior for sustainable future and create an environment for the activity ("Learning to be") of new agents promoting the SD ideas in their daily lives.

Actively considering existing critiques and challenges, systemic and individual transformations could be a pulsion for improvement of Education for Sustainable Development and SDGs achievement.

Figure 1. Mind mapping of students inputs on the SDGs achievement.

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